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Informal Knowledge-Based Learning Approaches Case Studies of Bio-Compost and Bamboo Production Promotions VONGSOUPHANH.A, SAYTHALATH.K, BOUDVISED.S and VONGPHONE.C Faculty of Social Sciences, National University of Laos

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ABSTRACT

This research “Informal Knowledge-Based Learning Approaches: case studies of bio-compost and bamboo production promotions” has two objectives. The first objective is to conduct knowledge-based learning approaches regarding bio-compost and bamboo production through the support from four nonprofit associations (NPAs). The second is to analyze the sustainability of the knowledge-based learning approaches based on four NPAs’ models. This research is funded by a Marie Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange scheme within the H2020 Programme (grant acronym: LABOUR, GA: 101007766) and collaborated by Participatory Development Knowledge Agency (PAKA). This is a qualitative research method and semi-structure interview with key informants is considered as a main research tool. In terms of data analysis, synthesizing concepts with main and sub themes are used. Describing and coding words are also applied to explain research findings. Results show that:

In terms of knowledge-based learning approaches, the four NPAs have applied a similar learning principle that encourages local peasants to explore and discover knowledge and skill practices within and between local community rather than to deliver new knowledge. From community development perspectives, this learning approach is called “local ownership principle”. This study considers that it is important to accept the principle of local ownership. Once local peasants have a strong sense of ownership and self-help, they will continue the work even after ending support from the donor projects. The four case NPAs studies have considered the importance of the local ownership principle by applying a process-based learning approach. Within this process-based approach, donors consider themselves as a facilitator, not an impetrator. Donors facilitate and encourage local participants to take control development process of the project implementation so they can learn, discover and solve issues during their development journeys. Moreover, the facilitation process also encourages more males to participate in gardening activities despite gardening work is likely considered as a female’ activity in the contexts of case studies. In addition, more women voices are being heard and considered by their partner because of more economic opportunities through gardening activities.

This study suggests some recommendations. Firstly, it is essential to acknowledge that local peasants are better learning by seeing and practicing rather than attending technical workshops with external expert-lead learning approaches. Thus, it is important that local authorities consistently encourage local peasants to exchange lessons. For example, peer to peer leaning group. Secondly, focusing on building model households that can influence other people is also important to prove the achievement of the project interventions with the time limitation. Thirdly, state support is necessary. State should play important roles in supporting relevant policies and works in conjunction with donor projects. While the state can provide policy directions, donor projects have potential technical and financial support so that together can make a better change for local development. Finally, this study would like to emphasize that process-based learning approach is more important than outcome-based development

approach. This study acknowledges that outcome-based indicators are important to prove the achievement of the project implementation. However, if the project intervention merely focuses on outcome-based

indicators, there is a potential that donors will apply the service delivery approach. Donors will not carefully listen to what people “see”. Therefore, what donors see is possibly different from what local peasants see. As a result, local people may be less active in participating in donor projects and stay back to the project after ending donor support.

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Introduction

Research Background

This research is collaborated by Participatory Development Knowledge Agency (PAKA) under the support of project collaboration “MSCA-RISE LABOUR – Project Number: 101007766- Tackling informal employment in Asia: building post-COVID19 solutions to precariousness through case-study based evidence on Bhutan, Laos, Maldives, Myanmar, Philippines, and Vietnam. PAKA is a social enterprise in Laos that serves informal education for youths, community members, school teachers, and local government authorities regarding diverse administrative management and technical skills. PAKA has received diverse funding resources, including from the PISSCA, French Embassy, to promote its informal knowledge-based learning focusing on sustainable development approaches. Other project partners, including Bio Compost Ban Phan Group (BCGP); Cooperation for Development and Support to Local Knowledge Association (COSKA); Community Development Association (CODA); and Bamboo and NTPF Development Association (BNDA), have also relieved some funding from PISSCA. These project partners are non-profit organizations (NPAs) that aim to promote and strengthen local knowledge and skills in rural communities with sustainable principles.

These NPAs have considered promoting bio-compost for organic vegetable and bamboo products as pilot projects. In fact, promotion on bio-compost and vegetable plantation for commerce are one of the agricultural development policies of the Lao government (MAF, 2016). Generally, Lao rural households plant vegetable for consumption but not for trade and they cannot consistently access market. It is important to promote small production groups so that they can learn and support one another to have better market accessibility (Department of Agriculture Extension and Cooperatives, 2016).

The four NPAs believe that the pilot projects can sustain local communities through many assumptions. For instant, firstly, these pilot projects assume that they can produce food so local peasants have natural food to support their daily meals plus with selling. Secondly, organic vegetable and bamboo products are demanded in markets, so those products generate household

income. Finally, these pilot projects are fundamentally related to local daily livelihood activities, even if not for trade but still for family consumption. Thus, the pilot projects can sustain local livelihoods.

PAKA acknowledges that each organization, including these four NPAs, has diverse development approaches to encourage local communities to get involved in project implementation. However, PAKA assumes that all NPAs would need to encourage local communities to participate in project implementation and take ownership so that local communities can continue to complete the work after ending support from donors. Therefore, PAKA is interested in examining knowledge-based learning approaches of local peasants regarding bio-compost and bamboo products. This study acknowledges that there are existing knowledge and skills in local contexts regarding bio-compost and bamboo products, and would like to understand how knowledge and skills have been promoted and by whom.

This research conducts four case studies and examine local experiences through four NPAs projects. The results are analyzed and discussed with relevant literature review. This study is cooperated by PAKA and a Ph.D. student, Amphone Vongsouphanh, from the Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Belgium. This research, however, is neither a part nor relevant of Amphone’ PhD thesis. Rather, it is general research that it is a part of LABOUR project collaboration.

This research will be useful not only for PAKA, NPAs, and government organizations but also for academic institutions. It provides rich information resources and critical discussion about gender empowerment and local sustainability.

Research Objectives

- a. To conduct knowledge-based learning approaches regarding bio-compost and bamboo production through support from four NPAs: BCGP, CODA, COSKA, and BNDA.
- b. To analyze the sustainability of the BCGP, CODA, COSKA, and BNDA development approaches based on farmers’ perspectives and practices.

Research Methods

Research Methodology

This qualitative research focuses on conducting life historical experiences of key informants (peasant farmers, village authorities, and project partners) regarding bio-compost and bamboo tree utilization and plantation. It aims to explore and collect knowledge-based education of local peasants and to understand how their existing knowledge has been developed and promoted. This examination helps researchers to understand what traditional local knowledge, skills and practices are promoted and existed in local contexts. This examination considers the importance of key-informant selection to get insight into stories of local contexts.

Research Tools and data collection

Semi-structured interviews with key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussion (FGD) are applied as research tools to collect personal stories of the KIIs and their perceptions regarding bio-compost and bamboo production and utilization. The interviews and FGDs are carried out at targeted villages in order to understand the real practical situations and the perceptions of the village peasants. The research team communicates with the project coordinators of the associations to explain the research purposes and tools, and targeted participants. After that, the project coordinators arranged for the FDGs and KIIs interviews. The FGDs and KII interviews are taken at the village site, usually at the house of the head of the village, village hall, or green-house farms.

Observation as observers (Mason, 2006) is also applied to both bio-compost and bamboo production and utilization case studies. Research team visits practical sites (Bio-compost production and techniques, organic vegetable farms, and bamboo production and farms), and the village peasants explain their working activities and producing processes. These visits help researchers to understand more practical exercises as well as stories.

Sampling Selection

Diverse key informants are selected. The first is the village authorities. In rural Lao contexts, it is essential to understand that village authorities, such as the head of the village and village administrative committees, play an important role in the social and political governance system. They are gatekeepers, and it is, formally, impossible to enter a village without receiving permission from village authorities. The village authorities are also, generally, knowledgeable resources, and often, they are the first participants of any project interventions, including the four NPAs case

studies. The second key informants are the village peasants, who actively participate in the project and/or have practical experiences and knowledge about the case studies. In addition, gender participation is also considered to understand diverse perceptions between males and females.

There are 54 interviewees in total, and 16 of them are females. 21 key informants have practical experience in producing bio-compost projects and these are members of the Bio-Compost Ban Phan Group (BCGP) project in Xienghuang province and the Cooperation for Development and Support to Local Knowledge Association (COSKA) in Phongsaly province. In addition, these 21 key informants, who are farmers, have been promoted by the BCGP and COSKA projects to produce bio-compost and utilize it for their vegetable organic gardening.

The other 33 key informants are those who have direct and indirect practical experience in making bamboo products and utilization. These members have been supported by Community Development Association (CODA) based in Savanakheth province and the Bamboo and NTPF Development Association (BND) based in Huaphanh province. These key informants are listed in the table 01:

Table 1. Number of key informants

Organizations	No. of key informants		
	Male	Female	Total
1. Bio Compost Ban Phan Group (BCGP)	7	6	13
2. Cooperation for Development and Support to Local Knowledge Association (COSKA)	7	1	8
3. Community Development Association (CODA)-	10	1	11
4. Bamboo and NTPF Development Association (BND)	14	8	22
Total of key informants	38	16	54

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The research team basically writes down the key discussion points on notes. In some cases, the research team applies memory techniques to make a flow conversation when the participants actively participated in the conversation. The research team also uses recorders to record the conversation and interviews with oral consent given by the participants. Later, all information and recordings are transcribed and saved as separate files. This transcribing technique helps researchers to enable to go back and check the needed information quickly and effectively. When it comes to

the analysis, “coding and thematic analysis with sensitizing concepts” is selected, which allows synthesizing of themes from data together (Van den Hoonaard, 2012).

Regarding data interpretation, main themes are generated into “subthemes” and they are described in relation to the main themes from one to another. This builds up on cohesion and flow of the findings and analysis discussion. Therefore, “direct narrative quotes” is applied for the result presentation, and a literature review is inserted into the analysis discussion (Mason, 2006).

Research Limitations

Having insight stories of the key informants is the strength of this research. The key informants are residents who have direct working experiences and are self-experienced with Bio-compost productions and bamboo plantation and utilization techniques. Thus, they could share their lesson learned through reflection on the issue. However, this qualitative study would have potential biases resulting from the selection of key informants, so its results are not representative for larger population. Furthermore, qualitative data can be subject to multiple interpretations, and this study is undertaken by researchers who are not from the region with deep knowledge of the culture of the study areas. To minimize this bias, researchers have the opportunity to cross-check the accuracy of the information with those experienced project coordinators who have been working with local communities for years. Finally, the interviews were spontaneously translated so that the meaning could have been lost or distorted in the interpretation process.

Research Findings

This research seeks to understand how local knowledge regarding bio-compost and bamboo products has been developed and improved, where they learn, and from whom? Through fieldwork visits, data collection, and analysis, research findings reveal that project-based donors play important roles in encouraging local peasants not only to study new knowledge and lessons from diverse resources but also to encourage local peasants to explore and apply local traditional knowledge and skills into practice. This research presents a brief summary of the four case studies so that readers can contextualize the study contexts.

Case Study 01: Bio Compost Ban Phan Group (BCGP)

The BCGP is a project funded by many NGOs, including PISSCA. The BGGP is coordinated by Paek District Agriculture and Forestry Office (DAFO), Xiengkhuang province. The project coordinator is a

government officer from the Paek DAFO. The BCGP points out that village peasants generally have a small vegetable gardening next to their house and used to utilize chemical fertilizers, which was harmful to locals’ health and the environment. The BCGP project aims to promote green and clean agriculture and the environment for local peasants. The BCGP assumes that the village peasants lack the knowledge and equipment to produce larger amounts of bio-compost that can be utilized for vegetable gardening, rice fields, and trade. Therefore, the BCGP project provides facilities and equipment, such as a compost machine, building a small house for installing bio-compost products, and installing electricity. The BCGP also educates administrative management and technical skills for targeted members. The education topics include providing techniques for producing bio-compost, leadership skills, marketing skills, group management skills, financing management skills, and advertisement skills through social media such as Facebook, radio, and provincial television.

The BCGP sees the needs of locals but also sees available resources from the locals that can be produced for bio-compost. Thus, the BCGP provides only the necessary materials, knowledge, and skills and asks the contributions from locals in terms of labor exchange and natural resources. Local participants utilize their natural resources, such as cow dung, waste fruits, weeds, and others, to produce bio-compost products. Usually, BCGP members (around 8 to 10 households for a village pilot project—ideally, each representative from each household) work together to produce the bio-compost products. The BCGP members work collectively together in this bio-compost house. They cut grass, weeds and put them together with dung and rice hulls into the compost machine. Some water and sugar are added. Those natural products are mashed up and mixed. After that, all the bio-products are put on the floor and covered by plastic bags. They leave it for 15 days before they flip over those natural products. The BCGP members have to wait 30 days at least before the bio-compost becomes organic fertilizer and ready to be used. Each time, the BCGP members produce between 1 to 2 tons.

The BCGP members take control of the process of producing bio-compost products. Both women and men participate in the production process, and the labor division is made. Males often take responsibility for heavy tasks, such as adding bio-products into the compost machine, removing them from the machine, and putting them on the floor. Most of the time, women are assistants for males helping to manage all the bio-products when they are on the floor.

Despite the fact that the BCGP project aims to encourage village peasants to produce bio-compost for sale, the bio-compost products are currently for utilization rather than for trade. This is because bio-compost products are not a popular choice for local consumers, and village peasants are likely to use chemical fertilizers for their gardening. Therefore, the BCGP members usually divide the bio-fertilizer outputs and use them for private gardening and paddy rice fields. Therefore, the BCGP members do not have any income from their bio-fertilizer products and use their private budget for each bio-compost processing. While most BCGP members confirm that they will keep producing bio-compost together and use the products for themselves, some of the BCGP members started questioning budgets for electricity bills and maintaining the compost machine when it is broken.

Case Study 02: Bio-Compost: Lesson Learned from Cooperation for Development and Support to Local Knowledge Association (COSKA).

COSKA is located in Bounneau District, Phongsaly province. The COSKA receives funding from NGOs and aims to promote household-organic gardens (HOG), and eight households have been selected to implement this pilot in Bounneau District. COSKA argues that the selected households will enable to produce vegetable products for family consumption and also for sale. The COSKA provides a greenhouse and seeds for each household member and there are two different styles of greenhouses (see figure 01).

Figure 1. Sample of greenhouse styles

The first style is a permanent greenhouse (see the picture on the left-hand side in figure 1); two families have received this assistance. This permanent greenhouse is a closed greenhouse and is covered by white plastics and metals. Thus, it can prevent insects or animals from getting inside and destroying vegetable products. This permanent greenhouse style can be last long for more than 10 years, according to COSKA. The second style is temporary and open (see picture on the right-hand side in figure 1). The COSKA only provides pieces of plastic to make the greenhouse roof. The village peasants prepare all other materials and wood to build the greenhouse themselves. They make a fence to

prevent big animals like cows or buffalos to eat their gardening products.

The COSKA works with Bounneau District Agricultural and Forestry Office (DAFO) to exchange some bio-compost approaches with local peasants. The COSKA also encourages village peasants to explore and apply their local knowledge and skills to produce bio-compost. As a result, each household has a dissimilar approach to making bio-compost products, but the bio-compost approaches can be grouped into two types.

The first bio-compost type is made on a concrete floor. A good example is the lesson learned from a female farmer. She has five years of experience in an organic vegetable plantation. The COSKA provided a permanent greenhouse, and her family spent around 2,000 USD for soil preparation and building a bio-compost house. The COSKA and Bounneau DAFO officials trained bio-compost skills and techniques for targeted village peasants, and she joined the training. According to her, the training suggested producing bio-compost on the ground, and she applied the lesson learned. She raises poultry, such as chickens and ducks, and pigs, so that she has dung to produce the bio-compost. Technically, she is advised by the COSKA that it is better to mix all dung from pigs and poultry with some water, rice hulls, weeds, and sugar and leave them on the ground floor for a couple of weeks. I would say that it is a similar bio-compost technique that is introduced to BCGP members. The difference is that COSKA does not provide a compost machine, so bio-products are mixed by hands.

However, after months of experience, this female learns that it takes months to compost and become bio-fertilizers. She decides to apply different techniques in practice. She makes a concrete floor inside the compost house. She claims that the concrete floor can produce warm temperatures, so there is much humidity to compost all composting products. She does not mix all the bio-compost components at once due to the lack of labor for help. Instead, she put all the bio-compost components on the concrete floor at different layers. The cow's dung is the first layer, followed by the dung of pigs (the second layer), and the dung of chicken and duck afterward (the third layer). She adds soil on top and uses plastic to cover it. She leaves it for the first week and begins to mix it, little by little, in the second week. She does not mix all the bio-compost products at once in the second week. Rather she continues to flip and mix them little by little when she has time. Usually, those mixed bio-compost products become organic fertilizer after week three, and she begins to use it. She

considers this practice as the best example of producing bio-compost and organic gardening in Bounnea district by COSKA as well as Bounneau DAFO. This kind of bio-compost technique is strongly recommended to expand to other households by COSKA and DAFO authorities, but there is no single household has applied her bio-compost skills. Rather, other village households apply different bio-compost techniques, which I explain in the second bio-compost type.

This female case study is recently considered by COSKA and Bounneau DAFO as the most successful example. She has successfully applied bio-compost techniques and utilized bio-compost fertilizers in her garden. As a result, her vegetable products are beautiful and fresh and become more and more popular among customers in the Bounneau district. Her customers are mostly government officials and business people who love organic vegetables. Her husband is a senior government official with good connections with government and business bodies. When there is a study visit for organic gardening in Bounneau, her organic garden will be the first choice to visit. She earns from selling organic gardening products approximately between 30 to 40 million kips per year.

The second bio-compost type is very much natural-based homemade. It is common to see households produce bio-compost in plastic bags or pieces of plastic next to their gardening in the context of the Bounneau district. There are no specific type and size of bag requirement but plastic bags are recommended because they can produce warm temperature. For the pieces of plastic to compost weeds are not specified any color or size, but depend on the needs of individuals.

COSKA encourages village peasants to explore diverse and easy homemade natural composts. Some village peasants produce bio-compost by mixing dung, and rice hulls together into plastic bags. The rice hull is burnt with fire, and make sure that hull is half burnt and half is not burnt. After that, they mix rice hulls and dung together, put them into bags, and leave them for a couple of months before they become organic fertilizers. Around four families have applied for this bio-technique, and they learned it from their parent's generation.

Village peasants mix all the weeds and grasses together on a piece of plastic. It is necessary that the plastic is big enough to cover all the weeds. Water is weekly checked and added, and it is important that do not let plastic dry. It takes five to six months before they are digested and become organic fertilizer. This bio-compost technique is introduced by DAFO authorities, and only one household has applied this lesson so far.

Another homemade-based bio-compost technique is to dig a big square on the ground (size depends on individuals' need) near the kitchen. All weeds, waste foods, and dung are added into the hole on the ground, and covers it with plastic. It takes three to four months to become organic fertilizers. This technique is quite simple, and it does not require much preparation. Every household can apply this homemade bio-compost technique for small gardening. However, only one household has applied this specific bio-compost technique. She learns this compost technique from her parents.

Case study 03: Community Development Association (CODA): Bamboo Plantation

CODA is located in Southern Laos, Savannakhet Province, and aims to promote local sustainable development concepts. With this aim, the CODA encourages locals to explore potential development projects that can be enhanced and developed by the local community. The commitment of CODA is to develop and promote agricultural products that have good nutrition for family consumption as well as market needs so that local peasants can earn additional income. CODA sees Bamboo shoots are very popular food for locals and are also demanded by markets. Thus, COSKA considers planting bamboo trees as another generating income resource for local peasants. Thus, CODA introduces this development project to Keokhamdee village and aims to implement it as a pilot project. There are 14 households participating in this project development. This pilot project is about to start, so it is too early to evaluate the progress. However, this study explains the process of how knowledge of bamboo plantation has been taken and applied to this particular development context.

This village is located in Xonbouly district, Savanakheth province. It is a Khmmu village, and the village peasants have no background in the bamboo plantation. Rather than introducing techniques and skills of bamboo plantations to local villagers, CODA applies a scaling-across-learning approach to encourage local participation. This learning approach is to encourage local participants to explore and learn from other farmers who have successfully implemented bamboo tree plantations. CODA invited all fourteen households to have a study tour and learn about bamboo tree plantation techniques in Savanakheth province. After that, CODA encourages local participants to apply the lesson learned to their own community project implementation. CODA has planned to provide some infrastructure development budget, including pump water, wire for making fences, and bamboo baby trees. CODA has requested locals' contributions to the

project, including land preparation and making wire fences surrounding the bamboo planting area. The village authorities provide a piece of land where all 14 households can work together collectively.

By the time of the fieldwork survey, this pilot project had been on progressing implementation. During the fieldwork survey, this study acknowledged that while village participants requested CODA to provide all the wire, water pumps, and bamboo baby trees, CODA confirmed that that would have no problem supporting those objects. However, the support would only be taken after the 14 households start to build up the fence and clear the land. The CODA argues that it is essential that the village participants initiate the implementation of the project and take all the development processes by themselves, which is known as local ownership principle. This study agrees with CODA that this development process can build on local ownership and commitment to work together between CODA and local peasants. However, collective action is not an easy job, and it is often influenced by benefit shares. When people work together at the same place, they share and exchange labor. It is common that while some people actively participate in project activities, others have less active participation, which becomes an issue when dividing project outputs. Those active people may ask for more benefits, but those inactive people may also ask for equal output division.

Case study 04: Bamboo and NTPF¹ Development Association (BNDA): Bamboo Products and Utilization

BNDA is based in Houaphanh province, Kouan district. The BNDA project works with 6 villages, namely Pakhome, Houybearn, Nonglao, Houyvan, Naor, Navin villages. Unlike the case study of CODA, BNDA works with villages that already have access to bamboo forest where local peasants can collect bamboo shoots for consumption and use bamboo trees for daily activities. BNDA promotes a concept of sustainable utilization of bamboo trees with the hope that village peasants will pay more attention to protecting their bamboo resources. To implement this concept, BNDA works with local authorities to raise awareness of the prevention and protection of local bamboo resources through two main activities.

The first is to manage the bamboo shoot collection. BNDA explains that it is true that village peasants used to collect bamboo shoots for consumption, but recently, more and more people have collected bamboo shoots for commerce. As a result, bamboo shoots in the forest

have significantly decreased. BNDA and the village authorities take action to manage the declining of bamboo shoot issue by issuing a village agreement on controlling the collection of bamboo shoots. The agreement states, according to a village head's statement:

All village households agree that collecting bamboo shoots in the forest for commerce can only be allowed from December to March each year. Other months are prohibited from trading bamboo shoots, but it is acceptable for family consumption. This agreement has been active since 2019.

COSKA encourages village authorities to establish a village safeguarding team to take responsibility for implementing such the village agreement. The village safeguarding team will monitor all village households and can take action for those households breaking the agreement. The agreement also agrees to collect an extra charge (200 kips per one kg of bamboo shoot) from trader and that extra income is used for administrative cost of the village safeguarding team. For instance, the price of bamboo shoot is 8000 kg per kg but traders have to buy at the price of 8200 per kg. While 8000 kips go to sellers (village households), 200 kips (tax charge) go to the village fund. This tax agreement has been one year of its implementation, and it is too early to claim its success.

The second is to generate additional income through selling bamboo products. Basically, many village peasants have skills in making bamboo baskets, bamboo rice boxes, and other bamboo products, but most of the time, they produce bamboo products for family utilization rather than for trade. The intervention of BNDA is to promote market access so that village peasants can sell their bamboo shoots and bamboo products to earn additional income.

BNDA selected 3-4 households from each targeted village to become trainees. BNDA has provided training of trainers (TOT) for local peasants regarding making a variety of bamboo products and group management. Those local trainees become local trainers continuing to train other village peasants. Those village trainees produce bamboo products for markets. BNDA is not a buyer or trader. Rather, BNDA plays the role as a community broker who helps to present local bamboo products and make connections to market channels. Through conversations with village authorities and peasants, this study found that many women and youths participate in making bamboo products and earn additional income for their daily consumption.

¹ Non-timber forest products (NTFPs) are any product or service other

than timber that is produced in forests.

These four case studies explain different community development approaches that have been applied to local contexts. The next section discusses the research findings. **Discussion and Analysis of the Research Findings**

This study presents the four case studies that promote small-scale development approaches for community development and enhancement. Research findings explain that the four case studies have likely applied a scaling-across learning approach rather than a service delivery learning approach. These two community development approaches are dissimilar (Westoby & Dowling, 2013). The scaling-across-learning approach encourages village peasants to explore and discover development journeys by themselves. Within the scaling-across role, donors usually consider themselves as a facilitator guiding and encouraging local communities to take control of all development processes. Thus, village peasants have a strong sense of local ownership and continue the project after ending support from the donor. In contrast, the service delivery learning approach focuses on introducing new ideas into local communities. Often, external knowledge and skills are introduced to locals. Therefore, external experts take control of development plans and play more important roles in the development process. As a result, village peasants do not actively participate in the development process, and local ownership is not strongly developed at the grassroots. Thus, village peasants may not continue the project after ending support from donors (Westoby & Dowling, 2013).

Considering the roles of the four case studies through these two community development approaches, this study argues that they have fundamentally applied the scaling-across-learning approach rather than the service-delivery learning approach. Firstly, the four case studies have considered the role of being as a facilitator rather than an implementer. Within the facilitator role, donor projects empower local communities to drive and implement project activities by themselves. Secondly, the donor projects train local peasants to become trainers and encourage local trainers to continue to train other village peasants regarding their development priorities. Thirdly, the project donors play the role as community brokers making connections between local communities and other development partners, including the government and market channels. Finally, the project donors play the role as monitor and supporter for development activities in order to ensure that assistance is provided according to local needs.

The scaling-across approach also opens spaces for donor projects to play the role of facilitator. This role is crucial for building the local ownership principle, the most important principle for sustainable development.

1.1. Local Ownership

Having explained that the main role of the four-donor projects is considered as a facilitator, not an implementer. Within the role given, these four projects have considered the unnecessary of the expert lead solution. Rather they have considered the significance of local-lead solutions. The facilitation process encourages the project donors to understand and pay attention to local experiences. Thus, collective agreement and action among village peasants can be made (Ife, 2013). As a result, local members will discover, develop, and manage development activities by themselves. This collective agreement process has been developed in the case study of BCGP in Xiengkhuang as well as the case study of bamboo utilization, BNDA in Houaphanh province. Lao peasants work together to manage their development activities.

The collective agreement can also be termed as collective practice meaning that to work as a group and give trust to each other. When trust is established, it can create an open space or a safe environment for discussion and enhance communication and cooperation more effectively. It encourages participants to share more about their concerns and problem-solving ideas (Westoby & Dowling, 2013)

In addition, the facilitation role allows project donors “see what people” (Buber, 1958). This is crucial from a community development perspective. Often community practitioners may not see what locals see and argue for the lack of understanding of the locals when coming to actions. The higher qualifications, moreover, may prevent a community practitioner from perceiving an actual fact because practitioners may work with a feeling of expertise that is fully filled by professional experts. Therefore, an assumption can often be made before they carefully listen to others (Westoby, 2014).

Furthermore, facilitation encourages local people to focus on a process-based learning approach rather than an outcome-based development approach. Ife (2013) highlights the distinction journey between these two principles. The outcome focuses on a destination, so plans are created and put in place as linear progress. The process-based principle, in contrast, is a journey of discovery. During the journey, a number of expected or unexpected experiences are encountered, and this discovery journey becomes more significant than the end of the journey itself (Ife, 2013). In addition, the

process is crucial because it can determine the outcome, and these two principles reflect on each other (Gandhi, cited in Ife, 2013).

The four case studies have considered the importance of the process-based development approach rather than the outcome-based development approach. The donor projects encourage local peasants to explore and apply new lessons as well as their traditional knowledge and skills to their development projects. For example, farmers have applied different techniques to produce bio-compost products. The techniques are not limited to the lessons introduced by donor projects but are also discovered through local experience and wisdom. The process-based learning pattern is essential for gender empowerment and local sustainability.

Gender Empowerment

Both bio-compost and bamboo products projects open more spaces for women to participate, learn and shift gender roles. It is still ongoing practice that women and men have different gender roles and cultural practices and beliefs play important roles in shaping gender roles. This study finds that women participating in donor-based development projects have better market access because they have more trading connections and opportunities to learn from outside their daily household activities. As a result, when women learn to trade, they can earn additional income. When women access diverse income resources, they are not merely based on the husband's earnings. Also, if females can access financial capital, they enable them to access markets (Alkire et al., 2013) and earn more income for their family, so their voices are being heard and considered. There are many example conversations to prove this shifting gender roles:

A male BCGP member argues that gardening activities are culturally considered as women activities in this local context. Women often have a small gardening next to the house. Males usually do construction work and work in the rice fields rather than gardening activities. However, the BCGP encourages males to participate in producing bio-compost products. As a result, more males cooperate in producing bio-compost products and utilize them for their rice fields.

A women participant in Bounneau district contends that usually women stay at home and they have less opportunities to exchange ideas in public. Most of the time males participate in village meeting. However, organic gardening activities open spaces for women to exchange gardening techniques with other members. Moreover, women have opportunities to welcome visitors visiting organic gardening. Women learn how

to communicate and share experiences with visitors. Women's voice is in public.

The Poverty Reduction Fund (PRF), Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, shares its experiences regarding shifting gender roles. PRF states that women's participation in public is less promoted in many remote areas. Participation is rather considered a men's role and responsibility. However, gender roles can be changed, and women's voices can be heard when women can access markets and become part of or key drivers for earning income resources and the family's well-being (Poverty Reduction Fund, 2019).

Moreover, the change in gender roles can contribute to not only promoting gender equality but also reducing gaps in gender equity. This contribution is noted during fieldwork observation and the interviews. Through the observations, particularly during the focus group discussion with participants in BCGP, the research found that two third of the participants were women. This phenomenon explains that women actively participate in public meetings through small-scale production groups.

This research acknowledges that most of the time, donor-based projects can potentially include more women participation. The projects can set up criteria for the participation of women and include more women than males or the opposite. It is essential that shifting gender roles should not be taken for granted. It is better to consider shifting gender roles as a learning process so local peasants, as well as local authorities, gradually learn and accept the change from time to time. Otherwise, the shifting gender roles can be considered as disrespectful or unacceptable behaviors that have significantly negative impacts on local livelihoods and cultural norms. The next heading discusses local sustainability.

Local Sustainability

Local sustainability can be a remaining question for donor-based projects. It can be true that most projects aim to apply a sustainable concept so the local peasants can continue the projects by themselves after ending support from the project donors. It is also a fact that donor projects have limited time and budgets to implement project intervention. Because of the limitations, the four donor-based projects support small-scale funding projects. Ife (2013) argues the importance of accepting the "small is beautiful" philosophy. Ife explains that it is not easy to apply this theory into practice because it means to minimize the growth concept while the nature of human needs is likely to emphasize growth and growth concepts. Even though limiting growth is challenging, it is a significant

concept for sustainable principle (Ife, 2013). This, in return, can bring in the notions of self-reliance, which is very important for community-driven development (Ife, 2013)

This study acknowledges that the four case studies have applied a process-based learning approach that can strengthen the sense of local ownership. Those four donor-based projects have also strongly encouraged the active participation of local communities with the hope that local peasants will work together. Thus, local contributions, both materials and labor exchange, are mandatory for the four case studies.

This study explains that the four case studies, particularly the BCGP and CODA, have applied a collective action principle (working together) through a labor exchange approach. In the context of market exchange, it is necessary to understand that people come to work and exchange labor through a "strict reciprocity principle" (Evans, 1990). By its nature, the strict reciprocity principle is monetized exchange from a capitalist system. That is, "one returns exactly what one is given," and of course, it is not difficult to manage since it is calculated by monetary calculation (Evans, 1990, p.141). This principal calculation can make a fair division of outputs for members based on labor exchange calculation.

However, with the time limitation, it is challenging for many donor-based projects to achieve their sustainable development goal for local communities. The fact that local communities take time to adapt themselves to new livelihood activities. More importantly, if the project intervention cannot clearly demonstrate the achievement to local communities, local people would potentially give up the work after ending support from donors. The four studies have presented some achievements but still ongoing processes of the project implementation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study acknowledges that donor-based projects can succeed or fail not only because of the time and budget limitations but also because of the implementation process. This study explains that it is important to accept the principle of local ownership so local participants will have more sense of belonging and ownership during the project implementation. Once local peasants have a strong sense of ownership and self-help, they will continue the work even after ending support from the donor projects. The four case NPAs studies have considered the importance of the local ownership principle by applying a process-based learning approach. Within this process-based approach, donors consider themselves as a facilitator, not an intruder. Donors facilitate and encourage local

participants to take control development process of the project implementation so they can learn, discover and solve issues during their development journeys.

There are many discovery lessons that four case studies have demonstrated, but they have not exchanged with one another even within the community. Therefore, this study suggests some recommendations.

Firstly, it is essential to acknowledge that local peasants are better learning by seeing and practicing. They want to see and exchange lessons through practical exercises rather than attending technical workshops with external expert-lead learning approaches. Thus, it is important that local authorities consistently encourage local peasants to exchange lessons. For example, peer to peer leaning group.

Secondly, producing diverse learning-material resources that local communities can easily access and learn effectively. For examples, filming videos of the successful case studies and post on social medial platforms such as Facebook, You Tube and TikTok.

Thirdly, focusing on building model households in communities that can influence other people. With the time limitation, donor projects have not much opportunities to achieve all tasks. Therefore, it is important to consider to having an example to prove the achievement of the project interventions. Other village peasants still can learn from the successful stories.

Fourthly, state support is necessary. State should play important roles in supporting relevant policies and works in conjunction with donor projects. While the state can provide policy directions, donor projects have potential technical and finical support so that together can make a better change for local development.

Finally, this study would like to emphasize that process-based learning approach is more important than outcome-based development approach. This study acknowledge that outcome-based indicators are important to prove the achievement of the project implementation. However, if the project intervention merely focuses on outcome-based indicators, there is a potential that donors will apply the service delivery approach. Donors will not carefully listen to what people "see". Therefore, what donors see is possibly different from what local peasants see. As a result, local people may be less active in participating in donor projects and stay back to the project after ending donor support.

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